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Development of a beam-type tidal turbine composite subcomponent for submerged fatigue testing

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Abstract

Composite materials are being considered for marine energy structures for their potential low weight and durability benefits. However, composites are susceptible to moisture intrusion when submerged, which can degrade their mechanical properties. Combining moisture intrusion with repeated loading from currents and waves could further diminish those properties. In previous studies, water absorption testing was followed by fatigue testing, which may not represent in-service conditions—when submerged composites are loaded, water may enter open fatigue cracks, and when the composites are unloaded, the water could further propagate cracks.

To better represent in-service conditions, a submerged fatigue test fixture is being developed. Prior to designing the test fixture, a composite beam was designed that met these design criteria: (1) has a load scenario like a tidal blade, (2) has evenly distributed stresses, (3) fails in the gauge section, (4) withstands tidal turbine blade design loads, and (5) can be tested in submerged fatigue conditions.

Stress value comparisons of tapered beam geometries with an isotropic material were performed. In addition to comparing beam geometries, comparisons were made between Ansys finite element models and cross-section analyses in MATLAB. The selected beam was a quadratically tapered-to-constant I-beam with a taper that ends at the mid-span. The composite beam was then developed in Ansys Composite PrepPost using the base geometry. Eigenvalue buckling load, Tsai-Wu failure indices, and strain values were measured in Ansys to inform composite beam failure load, location, and strain value reasonability, respectively. The eigenvalue buckling load was 33% higher than the design load. Tsai-Wu failure indices indicated the beam will likely fail in the gauge section. Strain values were 20% higher than those recommended in a wind turbine blade standard and 127% higher than those in the tidal blade of interest. Overall, all five design criteria were met. The composite beam designed in this study will be manufactured and tested in submerged fatigue conditions. Results from testing will be used to estimate the durability of composite marine energy structures under in-service conditions.

Keywords: composites modeling; marine energy; subcomponent testing; finite element analysis; submerged fatigue testing

1. Introduction

Marine energy converters convert kinetic energy from waves and currents into electricity. Marine energy converter types include tidal turbines [1], wave point absorbers [2], oscillating water columns [3], and surging flaps [4]. Composite materials are commonly considered across all marine energy converter types for their weight, cost,

and durability advantages [5], but deployment failures, such as during a tidal turbine deployment in 2006 [1] have shown that further research is needed.

Blade and other composite structural failures could be prevented through in-lab structural validation in simulated environmental conditions prior to deployment. Environmental conditions for tidal turbine blades include submersion and repeated loading. Structural validation of tidal turbine blade fatigue is commonly performed in dry conditions [6, 7], but, to the authors' knowledge, no tidal blade tests have been performed in submerged fatigue conditions. Structural validation could be sufficient in dry conditions, but no studies have demonstrated a 20-year design life met in dry fatigue testing corresponds with a 20-year deployed life. Until this correspondence is demonstrated, an understanding of the combined effects of moisture intrusion and fatigue must be developed to design and manufacture more durable marine energy structures.

A building block approach is being used for this study. The approach used has three steps: (1) selecting the material system and manufacturing approach, (2) characterizing small samples using experimentation and analysis, and (3) examining larger structures to characterize buckling behavior and combined loading effects. Each step is supported by a detailed analysis to prove the behavior of the structures are well-understood and predictable [8]. Steps 1 and 2 were completed by Lusty, Murdy, and Gionet-Gonzales (2024) [9]. For Step 1, glass fiber reinforced composite materials manufactured using vacuum-assisted resin transfer molding were selected. For Step 2, small samples of glass fiber reinforced vinyl ester and thermoplastic composites were four-point bend tested in dry and submerged fatigue conditions. There was a 69% decrease in cycles to failure from dry to submerged for the vinyl ester composites and a 42% decrease from dry to submerged for the thermoplastic composites. Although these drops in fatigue life were steep, the load values and scenario in this study were not representative of in-service conditions.

To better represent in-service conditions and to begin Step 3, a fixture is being developed to test beam-type tidal turbine blade composite subcomponents in submerged fatigue conditions. Beams were identified as subcomponents of interest to the U.S. marine hydrokinetic (MHK) industry and R&D from the wind industry [5]. To develop the fixture, a composite beam was first developed using the methods described in this study. The methods included selecting a beam geometry by comparing stress results among varying isotropic I-beams and then developing a composite beam using the selected geometry. The beam's design load values were selected based on the maximum computational fluid dynamics (CFD) load of the Open-Source Tidal Energy Converter's Marine Hydrokinetic Family 1 (MHK F1) tidal turbine blade, which will first be deployed with aluminum blades followed by a deployment with composite blades [10, 11]. Furthermore, the design criteria ensure the beam (1) has a load scenario like a tidal blade, (2) has evenly distributed stresses, (3) fails in the gauge section, (4) withstands tidal turbine blade design loads, and (5) can be tested in submerged fatigue conditions.

The beam cross-sectional shape selection, beam securement, and loading methods in this study were developed largely based on the setup used by Sayer, Van Wingerde, and Busmann (2010), which was used to evaluate adhesive bonds between the web and spar caps of wind turbine blades [12]. The fixture will be designed to test beams in a cantilever loading scenario to represent tidal turbine blade loading. Results from the analyses of the finalized beam will be used to inform the fixture's tank, saddle, and clamp designs. In addition to the increased understanding of combined effects, developing a series of test fixtures that range from the coupon scale to eventually the full-scale will enable the rapid implementation of new materials and design changes into marine energy structures and derisk deployments.

2. Beam Development

The beam was developed in two stages. First, a beam geometry was selected by comparing differently tapered isotropic beams and validating finite element models with cross-section analysis. Second, a composite I-beam was developed based on the selected beam geometry.

2.1 Isotropic I-Beam Geometry Development Methods

To develop a composite beam geometry, an isotropic beam geometry was first selected. To select the isotropic beam geometry, stress value results were first compared between MATLAB cross-section analyses to finite element results for an isotropic, steel I-beam with a constant cross section and straight centerline. Once there was agreement in the stress results between the two methods used, more complex geometries were developed.

Beam geometry types are ambiguously characterized in literature. The work of Balduzzi et al. (2015) was used as a guide to develop the terms, *linearly tapered-to-constant* (LTC) and *quadratically tapered-to-constant* (QTC) to describe the beam geometries examined in this study [13]. In tapered-to-constant cross-sections, the tapered cross-

section becomes a constant cross-section. In LTC cross-sections, the cross-section begins as a linear taper and ends as a constant taper. In QTC cross-sections, the cross-section begins as a quadratic taper and ends as a constant taper. The schematics of the two beam types are illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Linearly (left), and quadratically (right) tapered-to-constant beam top and side view schematics, in which L is the length of the beam, L_x is the taper length, w_1 is the initial width, w_2 is the final width, H_1 is the initial height, and H_2 is the final height.

CFD models of the MHKF1 turbine blade resulted in a maximum shear force of $P = 5.6$ kN [14]. This value was used as the maximum design load for the beam models. To validate the beam models with hand calculations, stress values along the top of the beams were compared. For each comparison, $w_1 = H_1 = 200$ mm, $w_2 = H_2 = 100$ mm, and $L = 1$ m.

2.2 Isotropic I-Beam Geometry Development Results

Isotropic I-beam geometry selection was determined by comparing the stress value results measured along LTC and QTC beams (Figures 2 and 3).

Taper Length (mm)	FEA	MATLAB
300		
500		
700		

Figure 2. Stress value results for linearly and quadratically tapered-to-constant beams for different taper lengths.

Figure 3. Color plot of the normal stress (z-axis orientation) along the top of the quadratically tapered-to-constant I-beam, where the taper ends 500mm from the root of the beam.

LTC beams had stress concentrations where the tapered portion met the constant portion, so the LTC beams did not meet design criterion #2. The QTC beams did not have localized stress concentrations. Both the 500-mm and the 700-mm QTC beams had evenly distributed stress and thus would meet design criterion #2. However, the 500-mm beam was selected to increase the likelihood failing both in the gauge section and the composite material, which would thus lead to meeting design criterion #3.

2.3 Composite Beam Development Methods

A composite beam was developed using the selected beam geometry in Ansys Composite PrepPost (ACP). Then, eigenvalue buckling loads, Tsai-Wu failure indices, and strain values were computed to estimate beam failure loads and locations.

The flange layup selected was $[0, 0, \pm 45]_s$ and the web layup included a C-channel with two $[\pm 45]_6$ laminates sandwiching foam. The beam was extended by 350.00 mm on the fixed end and 133.35 mm on the loaded end to accommodate the clamps and saddles in the test fixture. The materials used were Saertex unidirectional and biaxial reinforced epoxy composites, Araldite 2015 adhesive, and Gurit Corecell M-80 foam. The beam's mesh results are illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Mesh results for the entire composite beam (left) and the flange and web joint (right).

For the Tsai-Wu and strain analyses, fixed supports were applied on the clamped end and a 5.6 kN remote force was applied in the z-direction on the loaded end. The Tsai-Wu failure criterion [15] was used to understand the region of the beam that would be likely to fail first. The Tsai-Wu criterion predicts failure when the failure index in a composite laminate reaches 1.

2.4 Composite Beam Development Results

Eigenvalue buckling analysis resulted in a minimum buckling load of 7,887 N. This result predicts the manufactured beam will buckle at a load 33% higher than the design load, meeting design criterion #4. The maximum Tsai-Wu Failure criterion result was 0.24 in the flange, suggesting the composite is unlikely to fail at the design load. Based on the colormap in Figure 5, any composite damage during testing will likely occur in the curved portion of the flange.

Figure 5. Tsai-Wu results for the composite flange, where the maximum value was 0.24 in the curved section along the centerline. This result also indicated where there may be stress concentration between the fixed and curved sections of the beam. Chamfers were later added to the beam geometry to reduce stress concentrations.

The normal elastic strain values in the x-axis orientation were computed along the tops and bottoms of the beams, similarly to how the stress values were computed in Figure 3. The values were compared to MHK F1 composite blade structural test results and existing standards. The MHK F1 composite blade was loaded to 5.6 kN with strain gauges placed along its centerline. Its maximum strains occurred 900 mm from the root. Standards for marine energy structure strain values are limited, so strain values were compared to those from the DNV rotor blades for wind turbines standard [16] to verify strain values are reasonable for composite blade structure. The results in Table 1 indicate the strain values are within 20% of wind turbine blade strain recommendations and are 127% higher than the MHK F1 tidal turbine blade.

Table 1. Comparison between maximum normal strain values and standards.

Strain type	QTC Composite Beam Maximum Normal Elastic Strain ($\mu\epsilon$)	DNVGL Strain Limit ($\mu\epsilon$)	% Difference Between QTC and DNVGL	MHK F1 Experimental Maximum Strain ($\mu\epsilon$)	% difference between QTC and MHK F1
Tensile	2774	3500	-20	615	-127
Compressive	-2960	-2500	18	-658	-127

3. Conclusions

A geometry was selected and a composite beam was designed to be tested in a submerged fatigue test fixture. The composite beam met these design criteria: (1) has a load scenario like a tidal blade, (2) has evenly distributed stresses, (3) fails in the gauge section, (4) withstands tidal turbine blade design loads, and (5) can be tested in submerged fatigue conditions. A cantilever load scenario was selected to simulate tidal blade loading, meeting design criterion #1. Stress results from the 500-mm QTC beam demonstrated that the beam had evenly distributed stresses, meeting design criterion #2.

Since the strain results were 127% higher than those for the MHK F1 tidal blade, it is expected that experimental strain values in the composite beam will exceed in-service strain values for the tidal blade. The higher strain values will likely lead to damage in the composite, so the effects of the combined environmental conditions will be more likely to be observed during experimental testing. The higher strain values combined with the Tsai-Wu failure criterion colormap results indicate that failure in the gauge section is likely, meeting design criterion #3. The eigenvalue buckling load result of 7,887 N exceeds the design load of 5,600 N by 33%, meeting design criterion #4. The composite beam was extended on both ends to be fixed by clamps and loaded using a saddle so the beam can be tested in submerged fatigue conditions. Extending the beam on both ends thus leads to meeting design criterion #5.

Since the five criteria were met, the designed beam can be used for submerged fatigue testing. The composite beam design will be used to design composite beam molds and the submerged fatigue test fixture. The molds, beams, and test fixture will be manufactured and assembled to test the beams. Fatigue life, stress, strength, and strain value results from submerged fatigue testing the composite beams will be compared to the results of past coupon-scale submerged composite and dry composite tidal turbine blade testing. Those results and comparisons will be used to estimate the durability of composite marine energy structures under in-service conditions. The methods developed herein may be used to develop subcomponent designs for future marine energy structures. Results from submerged fatigue subcomponent testing will increase understanding of component durability and de-risk marine energy projects, in the effort to make marine energy a more resilient form of renewable energy.

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